

Bringing together African and European partners to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers.

SkincAlr in Senegal: Fieldwork, Recognition and Strong National Support

The SkincAlr consortium travelled to Senegal to conduct fieldwork and user research, while also [taking part in the national ceremony](#) for the *Célébration de la Journée Mondiale de Lutte contre Les MTN (World Neglected Tropical Diseases Day)* held in Khombole. This mission marked an important milestone for the project, reinforcing our commitment to ensuring that our AI-powered solution for skin-related neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) is firmly grounded in the realities of frontline healthcare systems in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Several key members of the consortium were present during the visit. Their presence enabled in-depth discussions, hands-on exchanges, and direct

engagement with healthcare professionals.

[Read the full article](#)

SkincAIr in depth

Hidden in Plain Sight:

How SkincAlr can help fight the most prevalent skin NTDs in Africa

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
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The project is supported by Global Health EDCTP3 and its partners.

Hidden in plain sight: how SkincAlr can help fight the most prevalent skin NTDs in Africa

On 30 January each year, [World Neglected Tropical Diseases Day](#) reminds the global health community of a simple truth: **no one should suffer from diseases that are both preventable and treatable**. Yet across Sub-Saharan Africa, **skin NTDs significantly impact everyday life**. Often dismissed as minor, these conditions can start with an itch, swelling or discolouration of the skin. However, if not recognised early, they can have serious consequences.

In primary care settings where dermatological expertise is scarce, even trained healthcare workers may find it difficult to distinguish between common rashes and serious infections or NTDs. **This is where SkincAlr comes in.**

Read more about how SkincAlr can help to fight skin NTDs.

Events

SkincAlr is presented at classes at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

On Friday 6 February, researcher Mario Bravo Cuadro participated at Dr Maria celia fernández aller's 'Ethical and Social Aspects' class at the [Universidad Politécnica de Madrid](#) (the project coordinator) to **introduce the SkincAlr project to the students**. He linked the project to topics covered in the course, such as professional responsibility and privacy.

[Read the full article](#)

SkincAlr partners

Teacup Lab role at SkincAlr

[Teacup Lab](#) is a UX research consultancy working with global brands. They contribute to improve the experience of products and services used daily by hundreds of millions of people. "This is our first time joining a European project, and we're super excited to pour all our research skills and experience into something on such a large scale, especially a project whose main goal is social impact, not just economics."

We would like to introduce you to Teacup's role at SkincAir through three articles that explore the various aspects of their work on the project.

Part I

UX Research for Social Impact in Africa

[Read the article](#)

Part II

The Value of Desktop Research in UX.

[Read the article](#)

Part III

Ethics in Research: Beyond the NDA

[Read the article](#)

SkincAir Project

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